

Table A.1. Ba-rich stars selected as Gaia-Sausage-Enceladus members, following Feuillet et al. (2021) selection, that were not considered in the analysis.

Gaia ID	[Fe/H]	[Ba/Fe]
Gaia DR3 2982933097213087616	-1.39	1.85
Gaia DR3 3686190458143012352	-2.04	2.40
Gaia DR3 2722263350106417152	-1.20	1.17
Gaia DR3 2601354871056014336	-2.09	1.55
Gaia DR3 2448568453248165504	-2.11	2.20

Appendix A: Ba-rich stars not considered in the analysis

To ensure the meaningfulness of the elemental abundance trends, we have chosen to exclude Ba-rich stars. These stars do not provide insights into a galaxy's chemical enrichment but are the results of the evolution in binary systems. Apart from being high in Ba, such stars can also have enhanced carbon abundances, due to a mass transfer from an Asymptotic Giant Branch companion. We, therefore, checked the C abundances in all stars and found that all the stars listed in Table A.1 exhibit both high Ba and high C abundances, and are therefore removed from our sample.

Appendix B: SAGA database literature references for Gaia-Sausage-Enceladus members

Table B.1 gives the literature references from which the stellar atmospheric parameters and elemental abundances are gathered by the SAGA database for the Gaia-Sausage-Enceladus members following the Feuillet et al. (2021) selection scheme. These are the stars used in the elemental abundance analysis and interpretation of the star formation history.

Appendix C: Elemental abundance trends for different selection schemes

For completeness, we show the elemental abundances and their derived median trends for the other five Gaia-Sausage-Enceladus selection schemes listed in Table 2. The error-bars represent the MAD for stars with multiple measurements of a particular elemental abundance ratio. These error-bars are not taken into account when deriving the trends. We also include the r -II stars and high-light them. They follow the general trends apart from that their Eu abundances are high.

Appendix D: Effective temperatures and stellar ages

Appendix D.1: Effective temperatures – additional checks

When estimating the stellar ages (Sec. 3.4), we opted to use the photometric T_{eff} instead of the SAGA T_{eff} . As mentioned above, the SAGA catalogue is a literature compilation, therefore stellar parameters are not homogeneously derived and some stars have T_{eff} reported from more than one study. This is not ideal for precise comparisons of stellar ages on a common absolute scale. In Fig. D.1 we compare the photometric T_{eff} calculated in Sec. 3.4 with the median SAGA literature T_{eff} . The standard deviation is

211 K and the mean difference is 161 K, suggesting an offset in the median SAGA literature T_{eff} with our photometric T_{eff} .

One could also consider using the Gaia RVS T_{eff} . We compare Gaia RVS T_{eff} with the photometric T_{eff} , Fig. D.1 b, we find the standard deviation is 27 K and the mean difference is 0.5 K. However, we decided to adopt the photometric T_{eff} for our Gaia-Sausage-Enceladus sample.

Appendix D.2: Age estimates for 13 dwarf stars with poorly constrained probability distribution functions

For completeness, we show in Fig. D.2 the probability distribution functions for the 13 dwarf stars, that do not meet our quality criteria, described in Sec 3.4. No age estimates are listed for these stars in Table 1.

Table B.1. SAGA database literature references used to obtain the median stellar parameters and abundances for each star selected using the Feuillet et al. (2021) selection scheme.

Object	Reference
2MASSJ00453930-7457294	Hansen et al. (2018)
2MASSJ02412152-1825376	Hansen et al. (2018)
2MASSJ03084611-4747083	Jacobson et al. (2015)
2MASSJ05254724-3049100	Sakari et al. (2018)
2MASSJ13164824-2743351	Hansen et al. (2018)
2MASSJ14043762+0011117	Sakari et al. (2018)
2MASSJ17273886-5133298	Hansen et al. (2018)
2MASSJ19202070-6627202	Hansen et al. (2018)
BD+06_648	Aoki & Honda (2008), Meléndez et al. (2001), Burris et al. (2000), Aoki et al. (2017)
BD+09_3223	Johnson & Bolte (2002), Johnson & Bolte (2001), Carney et al. (2003), Johnson (2002), Burris et al. (2000)
BD+19_1185	Boesgaard et al. (2011), Roederer et al. (2014), Roederer et al. (2010), Simmerer et al. (2004)
BD+26_2251	Fulbright (2000), Smiljanic et al. (2009)
BD-10_548	Ishigaki et al. (2012), Ishigaki et al. (2013), Ishigaki et al. (2010), Carney et al. (2003)
BD-14_5890	Ishigaki et al. (2012), Ishigaki et al. (2013), Charbonnel & Primas (2005), Ishigaki et al. (2010), Carney et al. (2003)
BD-17_484	Boesgaard et al. (2011), Ishigaki et al. (2012), Ishigaki et al. (2013), Ishigaki et al. (2010)
BD-18_271	Ishigaki et al. (2012), Ishigaki et al. (2013), Ishigaki et al. (2010), Carney et al. (2003), Meléndez & Barbuy (2002)
BS16077-0077	Allen et al. (2012)
BS16080-0175	Allen et al. (2012)
CD-45_3283	Nissen & Schuster (2010), Gratton et al. (2003), Caffau et al. (2005), Hansen et al. (2012), Smiljanic et al. (2009), Yan et al. (2016), Nissen & Schuster (2011)
CD-48_2445	Hansen et al. (2017), Asplund et al. (2006), Meléndez et al. (2010)
CD-57_1633	Nissen & Schuster (2010), Gratton et al. (2003), Hansen et al. (2012), Nissen et al. (2002), Tan et al. (2009), Caffau et al. (2005), Smiljanic et al. (2009), Yan et al. (2016), Nissen & Schuster (2011)
CS29512-0073	Roederer et al. (2014), Johnson et al. (2007), Masseron et al. (2012), Hansen et al. (2012), Allen et al. (2012)
G125-13	Nissen & Schuster (2010), Ishigaki et al. (2012), Ishigaki et al. (2013), Ishigaki et al. (2010), Nissen & Schuster (2011)
G126-62	Nissen et al. (2007), Akerman et al. (2004), Nissen et al. (2002), Roederer et al. (2014), Roederer et al. (2010), Simmerer et al. (2004), Fabbian et al. (2009), Asplund et al. (2006), Amars et al. (2019), Nissen et al. (2004)
G14-39	Ishigaki et al. (2012), Ishigaki et al. (2013), Ishigaki et al. (2010)
G161-73	Nissen & Schuster (2010), Roederer et al. (2014), Nissen & Schuster (2011)
G165-39	Ishigaki et al. (2012), Ishigaki et al. (2013), Shi et al. (2007), Ishigaki et al. (2010), Gehren et al. (2006), Boesgaard et al. (2005), Stephens & Boesgaard (2002)
G176-53	Nissen & Schuster (2010), Ishigaki et al. (2012), Ishigaki et al. (2013), Roederer et al. (2010), Simmerer et al. (2004), Yan et al. (2016), Nissen & Schuster (2011)
G18-24	Ishigaki et al. (2012), Ishigaki et al. (2013), Ishigaki et al. (2010)
G187-40	Ishigaki et al. (2012), Ishigaki et al. (2013)
G188-30	Roederer et al. (2014), Ishigaki et al. (2012), Ishigaki et al. (2013), Ishigaki et al. (2010), Boesgaard et al. (2005), Stephens & Boesgaard (2002)
G191-55	Boesgaard et al. (2011), Roederer et al. (2010), Simmerer et al. (2004)
G192-43	Ryan et al. (2001), Nissen & Schuster (2010), Boesgaard et al. (2011), Charbonnel & Primas (2005), Roederer et al. (2010), Simmerer et al. (2004), Meléndez et al. (2010), Nissen & Schuster (2011)
G23-14	Ishigaki et al. (2012), Ishigaki et al. (2013), Roederer et al. (2010), Simmerer et al. (2004)
G43-3	Ishigaki et al. (2012), Ishigaki et al. (2013)
G71-55	Roederer et al. (2014), Sakari et al. (2018)
G88-23	Roederer et al. (2014)
G9-36	Roederer et al. (2010), Simmerer et al. (2004), Boesgaard et al. (2005), Stephens & Boesgaard (2002)
G90-25	Roederer et al. (2014), Roederer et al. (2010), Simmerer et al. (2004)
Gaia DR3 4821671436294995456	Agúado et al. (2021)
Gaia DR3 6183013242623029504	Agúado et al. (2021)
Gaia DR3 751738088415866992	Li et al. (2022)
HD101063	Roederer et al. (2010), Simmerer et al. (2004)
HD110281	Li et al. (2013), Carney et al. (2003)
HD111980	Nissen & Schuster (2010), Ishigaki et al. (2012), Gratton et al. (2003), Reddy et al. (2006), Ishigaki et al. (2010), Hansen et al. (2012), Nissen et al. (2002), Fulbright (2000), Ishigaki et al. (2013), Tan et al. (2009), Smiljanic et al. (2009), Yan et al. (2016), Nissen & Schuster (2011)
HD126238	Roederer et al. (2014), Gratton et al. (2000), Sneden et al. (1998), Roederer et al. (2012), Hansen et al. (2012)
HD178443	McWilliam et al. (1995a), Roederer et al. (2014), McWilliam et al. (1995b)
HD184266	Ishigaki et al. (2012), Gratton et al. (2000), Fulbright & Johnson (2003), Takada-Hidai et al. (2002), Roederer et al. (2014), Ishigaki et al. (2013), Roederer et al. (2010), Simmerer et al. (2004), Carney et al. (2003)
HD20	Barklem et al. (2005), Zhang et al. (2011), Gratton et al. (2000), Fulbright & Johnson (2003), Carney et al. (2003), Christlieb et al. (2004), Burris et al. (2000), Ren et al. (2012)
HD210295	Alves-Brito et al. (2010), Ishigaki et al. (2012), Fulbright (2000), Ishigaki et al. (2013), Fulbright & Johnson (2003), Roederer et al. (2010), Simmerer et al. (2004)
HD213467	Jonesell et al. (2005), Ishigaki et al. (2012), Gratton et al. (2000), Ishigaki et al. (2013), Carney et al. (2003)
HD214362	Ishigaki et al. (2012), Ishigaki et al. (2010), Burris et al. (2000), Roederer et al. (2014), Ishigaki et al. (2013), Roederer et al. (2010), Simmerer et al. (2004), Carney et al. (2003)
HD216143	Aoki & Honda (2008), Fulbright & Johnson (2003), Saito et al. (2009), Mishenina et al. (2002), Meléndez et al. (2001), Burris et al. (2000), Mishenina et al. (2017), Mishenina & Kovtyukh (2001), Fulbright (2000), Johnson & Bolte (2002), Johnson & Bolte (2001), Johnson (2002)
HD222925	Roederer & Lawler (2021), Roederer et al. (2018), Den Hartog et al. (2021), Gratton et al. (2000), Roederer et al. (2020)
HD224959	Karinkuzhi et al. (2021), Masseron et al. (2010), Van Eck et al. (2003)
HD45282	Gratton et al. (2000), Shi et al. (2007), Fulbright & Johnson (2003), Saito et al. (2009), Mishenina et al. (2002), Mishenina & Kovtyukh (2001), Roederer et al. (2014), Fulbright (2000), Carney et al. (2003), García Pérez et al. (2006), García Pérez & Primas (2006)
HE0507-1653	Karinkuzhi et al. (2021), Aoki et al. (2007)
HE1305+0007	Goswami et al. (2006), Beers et al. (2007)
KIC10737052	Matsuno et al. (2021a)
KIC12253381	Matsuno et al. (2021a)
KIC5953450	Matsuno et al. (2021a)
KIC6611219	Matsuno et al. (2021a)
LP443-65	Ishigaki et al. (2012), Ishigaki et al. (2013), Ishigaki et al. (2010)
LP859-35	Ishigaki et al. (2012), Ishigaki et al. (2013), Ishigaki et al. (2010)
RAVEJ015656.3-140211	Sakari et al. (2018)
RAVEJ040618.2-030525	Rasmussen et al. (2020)
RAVEJ044208.2-342114	Rasmussen et al. (2020)
RAVEJ051727.4-134235	Sakari et al. (2018)
RAVEJ074824.3-483141	Rasmussen et al. (2020)
RAVEJ094634.8-062653	Sakari et al. (2018)
RAVEJ130200.0-084328	Sakari et al. (2018)
RAVEJ161228.4-054142	Sakari et al. (2018)
SMSSJ080050.54-724620.6	Jacobson et al. (2015)

"Sausage"

Fig. C.1. The Gaia-Sausage-Enceladus stars in the SAGA data sample selected according to the “Sausage” scheme. Different types of stars are identified according to the legend. The running median is also shown.

Helmi et al. (2018)

Fig. C.2. The Gaia-Sausage-Enceladus stars in the SAGA data sample selected according to the scheme from Helmi et al. (2018). Different types of stars are identified according to the legend. The running median is also shown.

Myeong et al. (2019)

Fig. C.3. The Gaia-Sausage-Enceladus stars in the SAGA data sample selected according to the scheme from Myeong et al. (2019). Different types of stars are identified according to the legend. The running median is also shown.

Horta et al. (2023)

Fig. C.4. The Gaia-Sausage-Enceladus stars in the SAGA data sample selected according to the scheme from Horta et al. (2023). Different types of stars are identified according to the legend. The running median is also shown.

Naidu et al. (2020)

Fig. C.5. The Gaia-Sausage-Enceladus stars in the SAGA data sample selected according to the scheme from Naidu et al. (2020). Different types of stars are identified according to the legend. The running median is also shown.

Fig. D.1. a) The difference between photometric T_{eff} and median T_{eff} in the SAGA database as a function of photometric T_{eff} . b) The difference between photometric T_{eff} and Gaia RVS T_{eff} as a function of photometric T_{eff} . In both panels, the colour-coding indicates the median SAGA $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$.

Fig. D.2. Age probability distribution functions for 13 dwarf stars selected as members of Gaia-Sausage-Enceladus according to Feuillet et al. (2021) scheme that do not meet our quality criteria.